

Technical Note

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Objective of the Technical Note	Introduction to the MRV4SOC consortium’s approach to establishing a baseline and further considerations, challenges, and recommendations regarding the CRCF regulation. In this document, we differentiate between the implementation at a project level and the way forward towards an EU MRV system.
Authors	Marta Gómez-Giménez (GMV), Arthur Monhonval and Romain Boulet (SC), Bas van Wesemael (UCLouvain), Bertrand Guenet (CNRS), Maria Fantappiè (CREA), Iryna Raikaya (UG) on behalf of the MRV4SOC consortium
Contact details. (MRV4SOC Coordinator)	Marta Gómez-Giménez (mggimenez@gmv.com)

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1. Background: CRCF definition of baseline: preliminary considerations for a European Voluntary Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification system in the land sector

7a)¹

- A standardised baseline should be representative of the standard performance of comparable practices and processes in similar social, economic, environmental and technological circumstances and take into account the geographical context, including local pedoclimatic and regulatory conditions.
- Such approach to establishing the baseline should be preferred because it ensures objectivity, minimizes compliance and other administrative costs, and positively recognizes the action of first movers who have already engaged in eligible activities.
- In the context of carbon (C) farming, only practices and processes that go beyond the common practice should be certified; therefore, a specific carbon farming activity should not be rewarded if it is already widely adopted within a region with similar pedoclimatic and regulatory conditions.
- The standardised baseline should ensure that, once an activity becomes the common practice, such activity cannot be certified any longer.
- To this end, the Commission should review at least every five years and update, as appropriate, the standardised baselines in light of evolving regulatory circumstances and of the latest available scientific evidence to reflect the social, economic, environmental, regulatory and technological developments and to encourage increased ambition over time in line with the Paris Agreement.
- However, where it is not possible to set such a standardized baseline, an activity-specific baseline based on the operator's individual performance should be used. The activity-specific baselines should be updated by the operator at the beginning of each activity period, unless otherwise stated in the applicable certification methodologies.

¹https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2014_2019/plmrep/COM MITTEES/ENVI/DV/2024/03-11/Item9-Provisionalagreement-CFCR_2022-0394COD_EN.pdf

1.1. Preliminary considerations regarding the CRCF regulation

- The standardised baseline for a given region should not be a single number (i.e., a specific level of net removals) derived from one or an ensemble of models if project developers are then free to use other (eligible) models to analyse performance against that baseline.
- Comparing different process-based models to a unique and independent absolute value will be to the advantage/disadvantage of a given process-based model depending on model structure and cal/val process.
- Setting the standardised management practices as the land management practices that are required by the regulation would provide an easy way to implement a baseline. This would also incentivise farmers that are going beyond the regulatory requirements at the time of entry into the carbon program.
- The inclusion of a list of positive effects on different ecosystem services could be considered to define the baseline, particularly, in peatlands.
- The use of available digital technologies should be promoted to decrease the costs of establishing baselines with the following acknowledgements in mind. Maps are associated to errors at farm scale (when comparing field by field as for carbon removal certification at the farm scale). This can hinder the incentive process for first movers with high Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) fields.
- Safeguards should be included to consider any long-term regulation modifications. A five-year update of the regional baseline could be done simultaneously to regulation modifications. However, the carbon program may not fit within the five-year agenda, hence safeguards for farmers during a given carbon program should be provided. The baseline should be fixed at the time of entry into the program and re-evaluated at the end of the carbon program only. The carbon program certification period should last five years before the re-evaluation of the baseline.
- The standardised baseline should be fixed at the time of entry into the program and re-evaluated at the end of the carbon program only (i.e., the baseline shall not be changed during the activity period). The Carbon program certification period should last a minimum of five years before the re-evaluation of the baseline. The EU Commission should re-evaluate the standardised baseline every 5 years.
- The determination of the baseline value should be done by an independent institution to avoid conflict of interest and possible misuse of the resource available.
- The standard SOC baseline will not be stable in the future, instead, will vary depending on the climatic conditions. Given the forecast of world temperature increase, it is

reasonable to forecast that the standard baseline SOC trend will be decreasing. This concept is explained by Peralta et al. (2022) (e.g. Figure 1). The expected potential storage in certain regions may change including higher carbon release. In MRV4SOC, we will consider climate change scenarios for understanding the impact of climate on SOC storage.

Figure 1 SOC theoretical evolutions under business-as-usual (BAU) practices and after the adoption of sustainable soil management (SSM) practices (Peralta et al., 2022, p. 9).

Practical example of potential impacts on how to set the baseline:

If maps only are used to set initial conditions in process-based models to define the standardised baseline, local scale heterogeneity in SOC content will shift the soil carbon storage potential (maps also entail errors for local scale estimations). For example: two farmers with different historical land management practices are willing to enter a carbon program in the same region.

- **A first mover** (regenerative agriculture farmer) has implemented sustainable land management practices for 20 years resulting in high SOC in their fields that are not standing out in soil maps (local scale errors). The standardised baseline will be set with low SOC as described by soil maps in his region whereas these fields have in reality a high SOC content. In addition, high SOC results in higher risk to lose carbon from mineralisation and lower potential to store C.

A first mover could get a lower reward in comparison to other farmers because of a lower SOC accumulation potential since they already have high SOC in their

fields. Those who started earlier may consider the approach unfair. One alternative could be that SOC already stored would be rewarded as already certifiable carbon credit, as if the certification project would have started in the past (that is, from the moment in time the farmer has adopted carbon farming practices).

- **A farmer in early transition** willing to implement sustainable land management practices but with initial low SOC in their fields, representative of the overall region as described with soil maps. High potential to store C.

Figure 2 Example of different cases to set the baseline value.

2. MRV4SOC approach to establishing a baseline at local scales

2.1. Terminology adopted in MRV4SOC: Baseline and Demonstration Site concept ².

MRV4SOC will be developed following a bottom-up approach based on 14 Demonstration Sites. The term *Demonstration Site* (DS) refers to areas located in different biogeographic regions for hypothesis testing and calibration/validation of methodologies. These areas will be used to identify baselines and compare results (benchmarks) to define a comprehensive and robust Tier 3 approach (i.e., scalable, accurate, transparent, standard, cost-effective, and reliable Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification framework for the EU land sector.

The methods to be developed in each DS shall quantify how an increasing number of areas managed with Carbon farming can improve carbon removals in comparison with areas exclusively managed with traditional management practices (business-as-usual). To assess the impact of carbon farming and traditional management practices on carbon removals, a *baseline* will be defined. The term baseline is understood as “a counterfactual against which the impact of a removals project is compared, i.e., the

² Deliverable of MRV4SOC: D1.7 Demonstration Site Guidelines v1.0.

baseline describes the carbon removals (and potentially emissions) that would have occurred in absence of the carbon removal project. The baseline can be a quantitative number (e.g., in terms of Mg CO₂-e) or can refer to a scenario (i.e., a hypothetical reference case that best represents the conditions most likely to occur in the absence of a proposed removals project)” (Bey et al., 2021, p. 4).

The DS are in five EU countries: Germany, Czech Republic, Italy, Belgium, and Spain; and one associated country: Norway. Those DS are within broad biogeographic regions that include Mediterranean, Atlantic, Continental, Arctic-Alpine, and Boreal (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Location of the MRV4SOC Demonstration Sites.

DS are representative of specific regional conditions. However, local conditions will have an impact on the determination of a baseline value. Therefore, two scales have been initially considered:

- **Sub-landscape scale:** farm holding level.
- **Landscape scale:** larger area representative of specific pedoclimatic, land use, and land management conditions tested at sub-landscape scale.

2.2. Definition of a standard baseline for MRV4SOC

The definition of standard practices in MRV4SOC at DS scale will focus on comparing traditional management practices (traditional tillage, crop rotation, conventional farming) with carbon farming practices (reduced tillage, long cover crops and improved rotations, wood plantation, new agroforestry).

The baseline will be set according to local pedoclimatic conditions at farm level and data availability from Long Term Experiments (sub-landscape scales). There is a wide range of time frames (starting date of the experiment) in different locations. Therefore, the type of management practices at larger regions may be related to different policy contexts (Table 1). Moreover, in some cases, the type of management practices changed over the years. Therefore, the definition of common standard practices is a key part of the assessment. The accuracy of the baseline SOC values will depend on the data availability. Especially, in terms of the availability of long-term data series with the same boundary conditions and land use type.

The representativeness of specific pedoclimatic conditions, land use, and land management practices assessed at sub-landscape scale will be identified to define a standard baseline for a larger area (landscape scale).

Table 1 Land cover classes, year of implementations, pedoclimatic, initial t0 considered (this may change during the implementation phase in some areas).

Land Cover	Country	Experiment Since
Agriculture / Croplands	BE	2022
	SP	1993
	IT	1994
		2014
	CZE	2019
	BE	2004
Grassland / Pasture	BE	2010
Agroforestry	SP	1997
	IT	2010
Forest	CZE	2019
	BE	1997
	NOR	1996
Peatland / Paludiculture / Wetlands	NOR	2021
	GER	2008
Peri-urban	SP	1998

3. Definition of a standard baseline for a European Voluntary Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification system in the land sector

In a wider context, we recommend that the definition of a standard baseline for Voluntary Carbon Markets in the European land sector should consider the definition of standard practices, the soil characteristics and pedoclimatic conditions, and how to prevent market friction when updating the baseline every 5 years. Further details are included in the following sections.

3.1. What definition of standard practices should be used?

Two options could be considered to define standard practices:

A) **As a minimum practice required by regulation.** This would simplify and reduce friction on the implementation of the baseline under different geographical context for different land use.

B) **As practices already widely adopted within a region with similar pedo-climatic and regulatory conditions.** This definition encompasses the regulatory minimum but would make the listing of such practices harder to define, especially, for a particular scale. In addition, this definition is not suitable to incentivise farmers with a high potential to sequester carbon (highly conventional farmers with already widely adopted sustainable land management practices in the region).

According to option A) the following scenarios could be taken into account (Table 1):

1. The Regulatory Minimum approach (Nitrate Directive).
2. The Regulatory Minimum + CAP GAECs (Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions) requirements.
3. The minimum + CAP GAECs + eco-scheme requirements.
4. Common practices using observational data or available datasets on practices (LUCAS + Copernicus) to provide methodical way to set “common practices” in a given region.

Table 1. Definition of standard practices

Option	Definition	PROS	CONS
1. Regulatory Minimum	Mandatory management practices under the Nitrate Directive (cover crop management mandatory by law for all farmers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to implement • Easy to understand • Easy to update • Standardised across EU • Most inclusive for all farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any practices required by GAECs could therefore not be considered additional for private sector funding, so reduced impact on mobilising finance • Lack of ambitious climate target (from NGO’s perspective)
2. Regulatory Minimum + GAECs	Standard practices include the one from the Nitrate directive + additional GAECs observed by farmers that choose to take CAP subsidies. (i.e., GAEC 6 soil cover during sensitive periods).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most farmers are getting CAP GAECs funding which represents most standard practices • Farmers can take rewarding both from private fundings and eco-scheme • Can still allow a layering and flexibility for different financing bodies. • Credible short-cut for additionality (most widely implemented practices are taken into account in the baseline). • Easy to deliver, update, defend (not black box) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to provide evidence that carbon certificates and eco-schemes are not overlapping (Eco-scheme do not reward enough to initiate a practice change from the farmer). • Is not per se taking common practices from a region into account.
3. Regulatory Minimum + GAECs + Eco-schemes	Standards practices include the one from the Nitrates directives + additional GAECs + practices incentivised via eco-schemes. Not yet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The baseline implemented using all these practices will be very ambitious. • More likely to keep environmental NGOS happy on ambitious target. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not all farmers are engaged into eco-scheme (so too ambitious) • A lot of farmers will not be rewarded because it is too hard to bridge the gap with baseline (too many regen practices set as baseline for majority of farmers).

	<p>known how widely adopted eco-schemes are (no numbers on area covered nor on efficacy for practice change).</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is not per se taking common practices from a region into account. • Eco-scheme are not rewarding enough to bear alone the implementation costs of a practice change for a farmer. If eco-scheme practices are considered standard, but the financial incentive effect of those eco-schemes is insufficient - as some analysis suggests - CRCF will become unattainable for most.
<p>4. Common practices using digital maps + LUCAS + Copernicus</p>	<p>The standards practices are defined as the common practices from a region using available datasets, observational data (LUCAS/ Copernicus/ JRC work).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fits with the current standardised baseline definition in the CRCF (beyond legal requirements and take into account common practices). • Most relevant way to incentivise practice change in the long-term. • May be even more relevant to fix soil characteristics (see next section) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Errors of digital maps (SOC) sometimes bigger than carbon removal range • What region boundary • What threshold for common practices (i.e., implemented in more than X% of the area) • Unpredictable, black box for farmers to commit or for buyers to pay). • Is the NDC updated on regular basis to allow standardised baseline update every 5 years? • Is the GHG inventory reporting relevant to translate common practices from a given country?

Challenges

These scenarios (1-4) were already suggested but not detailed in previous discussions. We could also include the possibility to use GHG reporting inventory by country for NDC on top of that to set observed practices or set baseline on other than soil related emissions for the baseline with the following barriers in mind: Is the GHG reporting inventory updated on regular basis to allow the standardised baseline to be updated every 5 years? Is the GHG inventory reporting granular enough on practices to translate into common practices from given pedo-climatic conditions?

As minimum practices required by regulation. This would simplify and reduce friction on the implementation of the baseline under different geographical context for different land use.

Recommendation

The best trade-off in the 4 options presented above from a Voluntary Carbon Market's perspective is **Option number 2**.

- Option 2 sets a baseline taking in consideration the most widely adopted set of practices farmers are already incentivised for or legally forced to do. This option is providing clarity on the way a standardised baseline is built (accepted by farmers) and what standard practices are going beyond regulation. This option prevents arbitrary set-up of common practices in different regions using black box methodology, lowering predictability for farmers and corporates together with commitment.
- The common practice option (Option 4) could be more relevant on a mid-term timescale but would not be sufficient on its own as it is currently existing (lack of data for certain practices coverage – i.e., cover cropping). Setting option 2 now will catalyse all farmers to transition to regenerative practices and be rewarded for it. In the mid-term, when regen practices will be more widely implemented, option 4 as a complementary option will appear as a good upgrade to prevent additionality issue and to continue improvement beyond common practices.
- We recommend option 2 in the immediate and short term. In parallel, observational data on common practices assessment in the different regions should be monitored with JRC inputs. On the mid-term, in 5 or 10 years, when regen practices become more and more widely implemented, the standardised baseline should reflect the common practices from every region. This will allow for continuous improvement to more sustainable practices by farmers.
- We also argue that tailoring the standard practices based on each farmer context (i.e., whether a farmer is applying GAEC and/or other eco-schemes) will be more and more

perceived as an individual baseline. Lack of predictability + perverse incentive to accept eco-scheme after standardised baseline is settled.

3.2. How to set the soil characteristics within different pedo-climatic conditions for the baseline and accurately take into account the carbon dynamic

- Should the soil characteristics used to set the baseline be the most representative of the region (e.g. average SOC content, most representative soil type, etc.) or should the soil characteristics represent the farmer's reality?
- The first solution bears the risk of penalising or even excluding early first movers to be rewarded for their work. Indeed, in most regions of France and Belgium, or in Northern Germany, SOC content is quite low, lying between 8 and 15 g kg⁻¹ on average. These low SOC soils have low mineralisation rates and therefore for an identical set of management practices, these soils emit less CO₂ than high SOC soils. If such SOC contents are used to set the standardised baseline, early first movers having locally increased the carbon contents of their soils with the long-term implementation of carbon farming practices will be penalised because of their higher mineralisation rate.
- The second will decrease this risk. But it bears the risk of transforming the standardised into a sort of individual baseline, i.e. standard practices combined with individual soil characteristics. If the soil characteristics of the farm are taken into account, the farmer will still have to go beyond standard practices to be rewarded but it will be adapted to his own soil reality, therefore comparing apples with apples. It means that the early movers will be incentivised to at least maintain the regenerative practices they put in place in the past. The first solution could be counterproductive on that matter.

Recommendation

A compromise for soil characteristics could be to set a fix standard set of parameters for which digital maps are accurate enough or for which direct soil sampling cannot replace digital maps or remote sensing data due to high costs. Namely characteristics such as soil texture, bulk density could be set on a regional basis (most representative in a given region). Other types of parameters (i.e., SOC) that are more heterogeneous or lack of field scale accuracy using regional maps should be set using field's reality and rely only on soil sampling. Once the accuracy of remote sensing for SOC at field scale is guaranteed, an alternative to soil sampling could be discussed.

3.3. How to update the standardised baseline every 5 years preventing market friction

Baseline should be fixed at the time of entry into the program and re-evaluated at the end of the carbon program only. Carbon program certification period should last five years before re-evaluation of the baseline. The EU commission should re-evaluate the baseline every 5 years (Figure 4).

SCC Year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Regional baseline	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
Cohort 1 farmer baseline	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
Cohort 2 farmer baseline	White	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
Cohort 5 farmer baseline	White	White	White	White	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Blue
Cohort 6 farmer baseline	White	White	White	White	White	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue

Figure 4. Standardised baseline update

Recommendation

The best option to avoid friction would be to update the standardised baseline using the highlighted methodology (Figure 4).

4. Further Challenges and Gaps

Some questions for discussion:

- What is *standard performance* of comparable practices? Are conventional and Regenerative Agriculture farmers considered as similar activities with similar practices?
- What would be the best way to address farmers in the middle of a carbon program when a baseline is re-evaluated (every 5 years according to the CRCF). Are farmers allowed to keep the baseline set at the time of their entry in the program?

References

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5. Annex I. Further agreement with MaRViC's recommendations regarding CRCF baselines³:

We agree with MaRViC's interpretation considering that the most conventional farms are not well served by a standardised baseline. Keeping in mind that conventional farms have low organic carbon content in their soil and therefore have the greatest potential for C sequestration. The standardised baseline will hardly incentivise them to change their current land management practices.

Regarding MARVIC's interpretation of the standardised baseline characteristics: "applying average (standardized) cropping practices to the specific conditions of the farm (specific soil conditions: soil type and initial level of Soil Organic Carbon, SOC) to calculate what the carbon storage dynamics of that farm would be if it had the standardized practices". This would unfold in creating as many "standardized" baselines as the number of conditions (i.e., crop specific). Leading to potential difficulties for farmers (and project developers) to predict where a farm's GHG balance stands regarding this "standardized baseline". This would prevent commitment from farmers to change their practices because of no guarantee to obtain a financial incentive.

Concern: MARVIC is suggesting an approach that would lead in as many baselines as number of soil conditions. This would create a major barrier for farmer's commitment because of unpredictability. Therefore, we disagree with MARVIC regarding this point. Hence, we foster a compromise between the soil characteristics that are fixed by digital maps (BD, texture) or specific to each farm (initial SOC).

The MaRViC's proposal of giving the project developer the right to choose between a standardised and individual baselines depending on the conditions of the farmer will incentivise early adopters to improve their practices and pioneers to maintain their practices.

³ **CRCF: recommendations on 8 key points regarding baselines**, based on the amended version of the CRCF of 11/10/2023 By the MARVIC project consortium 06/11/2023, sent to the Expert Group on C removals.

